

RELATIONSHIP OF CARBON FIBER SURFACE

COMPOSITION TO SURFACE ENERGY

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ABSTRACT:

Inverse gas chromatography (IGC) was applied for the determination of the surface energy and acidity-basicity properties of a series of commercial sized carbon fibers. The surface chemical composition of the carbon fibers was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The dispersive surface energy γ_s^D was calculated and found to range from 31.02 mJ/m² to 33.11 mJ/m². The specific surface energy γ_s^{SP} of the carbon fibers ranged from 5.44 mJ/m² to 17.61 mJ/m² and increased linearly with the increase of the percentage singly oxygen-containing groups present on the carbon fiber surface (other ratios also correlated well). The carbon fibers were found to exhibit a dominant acidic nature and exhibited a better correlation with the total carbon-oxygen functional groups content.

INTRODUCTION

The carbon fiber-reinforced composites (CFRC) take advantage of the high strength and high stiffness of fibers and display specific properties suitable for designed applications. Many aspects of the complicated CFRC manufacturing processes are still not understood

clearly in nowadays but it is generally accepted that an improvement of the performance of CFRC is possible by tailoring the surface properties of the carbon fiber [1-5].

The commercial carbon fibers are often sized to protect fiber from fuzzing and fragmenting. Sizing can also change the surface chemical structure of carbon fiber and improve the fiber-matrix interfacial adhesion [6].

The surface energy of carbon fiber consists of the dispersive surface energy γ_s^D and the specific surface energy (or called polar surface energy) γ_s^{SP} . The γ_s^{SP} relates to the polar or Lewis acid-base component of carbon fiber surface. Vikers noted that a strong acid-base interaction at the solid-liquid interface will minimize the surface free energy of the interface and enhance the wettability of carbon fiber. The acidity and basicity properties can be described by K_a and K_b , which are reflected the acidity (electron acceptor) and basicity (electron donor) of the solid surface. The surface acidity-basicity of carbon fiber is important to evaluate the intermolecular interaction for a fiber-resin system. Schultz proved that acid-base interactions have a strong influence on the interfacial shear strength for untreated and modified carbon fibers in epoxy matrix. The relationship of carbon fiber surface composition to surface energy and acidity-basicity properties is important for the measure of the wettability and interfacial adhesion of the fiber-matrix system [7].

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) has been proved as an available analytical technique for investigating the surface chemistry of carbon fiber. A series of detail studies on carbon fiber with XPS have been reported by Sherwood groups [8-10]. The surface energy and acidity-basicity properties of carbon fiber can be determined by inverse gas chromatography (IGC) [11-12]. After the introduction and subsequent theoretical developments, IGC has been used for the surface characterization of a wide range of materials, especially polymers, fibers and nano materials [13-15]. With the variety of probes, IGC can give realistic estimates for surface energy, as well as the acidity-basicity and other properties of materials under investigation. The reliability of the technique has been proven by many studies.

In this study, the surface chemistry of a series of commercial polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fibers were measured by XPS. The surface energy and acidity-basicity properties of these carbon fibers were determined by means of IGC. The relationship between surface chemical composition and surface properties were explored.

1. EXPERIMENTAL PART

1.1 Materials

The samples tested in this study are commercially sized polyacrylonitrile based carbon fibers: T300B-3000-40B (T1), T300B-6000-50B (T2), T700SC-12000-50C (T3) and T800HB-12000-40B (T4) sourced from Torayca. The solvents used in IGC were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. All these adsorbates were HPLC grade or high purity solvents and used as purchased.

1.2 Apparatus and procedure

1.2.1. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

XPS spectra were acquired on a ThermoFisher Scientific Excalab 250 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer. Data was recorded using monochromated Al K α radiation and the sensitivity was 180000cps. The base pressure was approximately 5.0 \times 10⁻⁹ mbar. The pass energies were 150 eV and 30 eV, for survey and high resolution spectra, respectively. The C1s binding energy of the graphitic peak was fixed at 284.6 eV for calibration purposes. Peak fitting of the XPS spectra was carried out using a XPSPEAK software with a Gaussian-Lorentzian (G/L) fitting function and a nonlinear background. The G/L mix was assumed to be 70% for all peaks.

1.2.2. Inverse gas chromatography

Inverse gas chromatography experiments were carried out at infinite dilution with an IGC equipment by Surface Measurement Systems. The neutral probes in these investigations were decane, nonane, octane and heptane, and the polar probes included toluene, dichloromethane, ethanol, dioxane and acetone. Data relating to all probes is presented in Table 1. The samples were placed into a passivated glass column of 4 mm internal diameter and 300 mm length, which supplied by SMS. The amount of carbon fiber was 0.8g in all columns. Methane was used as a non-interacting marker for dead-time measurements. Helium was used as carrier gas, and the flow rate was 10 ml/min. The adsorption experiments were carried out at 30°C. The data calculation was made by the SMS-IGC advanced analysis software (v1.2.5).

Table 1 Properties of the probes used in the current work

Probe	properties	DN	AN*	Surface Tension (J/m ²)	Cross Sectional Area (m ²)
n-Heptane	Neutral	-	-	0.0234	7.5E-19
n-Octane	Neutral	-	-	0.0227	6.9E-19
n-Nonane	Neutral	-	-	0.0213	6.3E-19
n-Decane	Neutral	-	-	0.0203	5.73E-19
Toluene	Base	20.3	14.33	0.0285	4.6E-19
Dichloromethane	Acid	0	3.9	0.0245	2.45E-19
Ethanol	Acid	20.0	10.3	0.0211	3.53E-19
1,4-Dioxane	Base	14.8	4.32	0.0332	3.14E-19
Acetone	Base	17.0	2.5	0.0165	3.4E-19

2. IGC theory

IGC allows the measurements of adsorption at very low vapor concentrations, where the adsorbate–adsorbate interactions are negligible. As in analytical gas chromatography, the retention time was as primary information. The retention time can be converted into a retention volume, which is directly related to various physico-chemical properties of the material.

The net retention volume V_R^0 determined by Equation 1:

$$V_R^0 = j/m \cdot F \cdot (t_R - t_0) \frac{T}{273.15} \quad (1)$$

where T is the column temperature, m is the sample mass, F is the carrier gas flow rate, t_R is the retention time taken for the probe and t_0 is the time necessary for a nonadsorbing probe

(methane) through the column (dead time), j is the James-Martin correction, which depend on the pressure at column inlet and outlet.

According to the method of Schultz [16], the γ_s^D can be derived from the slope of a series of alkanes' RTlnV plot to $a\sqrt{\gamma_L^D}$.

$$RT \ln V_R^0 = 2aN_A \sqrt{\gamma_s^D \gamma_L^D} + const \quad (2)$$

The interactions between polar probes and the substrate involve both dispersive and specific interactions, while the latter is usually assumed from the acid–base interaction solely.

$$\Delta G = \Delta G^d + \Delta G^{SP} \quad (3)$$

The acidic or basic probes' respective free energy of adsorption is different from the alkane probes'. As proposed by Donnet et al [17-18], RTlnV for each probe is plotted against its molar deformation polarization of the probe. The alkanes only have dispersive interactions and a linear relationship is obtained. The distance between each polar probe's point and the straight line represents the specific interaction, ΔG^{SP} .

The acceptor and donor parameters are related to the specific free energy by equation (4).

$$\Delta G^{SP} = 2aN_A (\sqrt{\gamma_L^+ \gamma_S^-} + \sqrt{\gamma_L^- \gamma_S^+}) \quad (4)$$

γ_L^+ and γ_L^- are the electron acceptor and donor parameters of the probe molecule, γ_s^+ and γ_s^- are the electron acceptor and electron donor parameters of the surface. If monopolar probe molecules are used, the γ_s^{SP} can be calculated from equation (5).

$$\gamma_s^{SP} = 2\sqrt{\gamma_s^+ \gamma_s^-} \quad (5)$$

Several approaches have been used to describe acidic and basic property of the solid surface [19-22]. Therefore, the Gutman Donor-Acceptor model is more frequently applied in IGC studies, as showed in equation (6).

$$\Delta G^{SP} \approx \Delta H = K_a * DN + K_b * AN^* \quad (6)$$

where the constants K_a and K_b characterise the ability of the solid sample to accept(acid) or to donate(basic) electrons. DN and AN^* are the donor and acceptor numbers of the probe molecule. To obtain K_a and K_b , ΔG^{SP} must be calculated for two or more probe molecules. Thus, the parameters can be determined by equation (7):

$$\frac{\Delta G^{SP}}{AN^*} = K_a \frac{DN}{AN^*} + K_b \quad (7)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Surface Chemical composition

An example of the XPS survey spectra for T1 fiber was shown in Figure 1. These samples showed intense C1s peak at $\approx 285\text{eV}$ and O1s peak $\approx 530\text{eV}$. The N1s peak was of very low intensity on T1 and T4 carbon fibers at $\approx 400\text{eV}$ and could not be detected for the T2 and T3 fibers. The results meant that the major element on these fibers' surface was carbon, and the second most concentrated element was oxygen. The T1 and T4 fiber also exhibited nitrogen while the T2 and T3 fibers had no nitrogen. The surface compositions of T1, T2, T3 and T4 carbon fibers were collected in Table 2. The work of Lindsay [11] showed that a correlation between γ_s^D and the oxygen percentage level at the surface of carbon fiber which exposed to an oxidative electrochemical surface treatment of varying degrees. As shown in table 2, the content of oxygen for T1, T2, T3 and T4 carbon fibers decreased in the order: T3 > T2 > T1 > T4.

Fig.1 The XPS survey spectrum for T1 carbon fiber

Table 2 Surface elemental analysis of carbon fibers

Name	C (%)	O (%)	N (%)	Si (%)
T1	76.73	18.96	3.70	0.61
T2	78.39	21.61	-	-
T3	79.94	19.60	-	0.46
T4	77.82	18.01	3.50	0.67

The types of oxygen-containing functional groups on the fiber as estimated by surface C1s spectra peak fitting are shown in table 3. The C1s spectra showed one main graphitic peak at 284.6 eV and three oxide peaks which shifted by 1.7, 4.7, and 7.0 eV from the graphitic peak, respectively. Peak 2 (oxide 1, 286.3eV) was assigned to $-\text{C}^*-\text{O}$ and C^*-OH and epoxy groups, peak 3 (oxide 2, 289.3eV) corresponded to $\text{C}^*=\text{O}$, C^*OOR and C^*OOH groups, peak 4 (oxide 3, 291.6eV) was probably ionized carboxyl $\text{C}^*\text{OO}-$ type groups and the $\pi-\pi^*$ shake up satellite. The curve fits performed for the data tow were constrained within very close limits in binding energy ($\pm 0.02\text{ eV}$) and full width at half maximum (FWHM) ($\pm 0.02\text{ eV}$) in this study. Example of peak fitted for T1 fiber was shown in Figure 2. The percentages of the total C1s

were shown in Table 3. The oxides area is related to the mount of total singly, doubly and multiply bound carbon-oxygen functional groups on fiber surface, which can be defined as total peak area of peak 2, peak 3 and peak4. As can be seen from the table 3, the oxides area for T1, T2, T3 and T4 decreased in the order: T2 > T3 > T1 > T4.

Fig.2 The C1s peak fitting for T1 carbon fiber

Table 3 Contents of different chemical groups on carbon fibers by C1s peak fitting

name	peak1	peak2	peak3	peak4	oxides area (2+3+4)/%
[Shift,FWHW]	[0,1]	[1.7,1.2]	[4.7,1.4]	[7,1.4]	
T1	56.21%	40.06%	2.94%	0.79%	43.79
T2	53.08%	44.83%	1.40%	0.70%	46.92
T3	53.23%	44.29%	1.70%	0.77%	46.77
T4	59.11%	37.36%	2.52%	1.01%	40.89

3.2 Surface properties by IGC

The surface energies of T1, T2, T3 and T4 carbon fibers were determined by using the method described in the section 2 and showed in figure 2.

As can be seen from the figure 2, the γ_s^D of the carbon fibers were from 31.02 mJ/m² to 33.11 mJ/m² and exhibited little significant variation. Other studies on the γ_s^D of PAN based carbon fibers have been reported in the literature. The work of Schultz et al. [16] showed that the γ_s^D of T300 carbon fiber obtained by IGC method was 50 mJ/m². This difference could be responded to the different experiment temperature and column material. Dichloromethane and Toluene were used as acidic and basic probes to measure the γ_s^{SP} of carbon fibers in this work. The γ_L^+ of dichloromethane is 124.58 mJ/m² and the γ_L^- is zero. The γ_L^+ of toluene is zero and the γ_L^- is 16.23 mJ/m². As can be seen from the figure 2,

distinct differences were founded for the γ_s^{SP} of the fibers, the T4's γ_s^{SP} was 7.73 mJ/m² and the T2's γ_s^{SP} was 20.91mJ/m².

The Ka and Kb of carbon fibers were calculated from the ΔG^{SP} of toluene, ethanol, dioxane, acetone and shown in figure 3. The surface of the carbon fibers showed dominance in the acidic nature on the fiber surface, for the existing of amount of carboxyl groups and Lewis acid groups, such as hydroxyls and aromatic rings, and they all contributed to the total acidity of the surface. These findings are in agreement with other previous works [22].

Fig.3 The acidic and basic property for the carbon fibers

3.3 Surface Chemistry and Surface Property

Figure 3 shows the trend of the dispersive surface energies versus their corresponding oxygen concentration of fibers. Lindsay et al. [11] found a correlation between oxygen percentage levels at the carbon surface. Unfortunately we do not find the obvious linear relationship between the γ_s^D and the oxygen concentration. One possible interpretation for this is that the carbon fibers used in Lindsay' work were unsized, and there was a remarkable difference between unsized and sized fiber. Correlations of γ_s^D with other surface composition were attempted, but no significant pattern was observed. Additional research is needed to verify these results.

Fig.3 Dispersive surface energies versus the oxygen concentration of fibers

The curve of the γ_s^{SP} versus their corresponding oxygen concentration of fibers is shown in figure 4A. As a result, it can be seen that the specific component of surface free energy increases with increasing the oxygen percentage level at the carbon surface with a correlation of 0.773. As considering the relation of the total nitrogen and oxygen concentration with the γ_s^{SP} of carbon fibers, no obvious correlation was obtained (figure 4B). In order to eliminate the infection of the chemisorbed oxygen on the fiber, the specific surface energy values were plotted against the oxides area, a correlation of 0.986 was obtained (figure 4C). This ratio reflects the amount of oxide functional groups, including hydroxyl, epoxy, ether, carbonyl and carboxyl groups. A strong relationship between the specific surface energy and the peak2 ratio was observed with a correlation of 0.998 (figure 4D). The results show that the γ_s^{SP} of carbon fibers increase with the increasing of the concentration of peak 2 and the singly oxygen-containing groups dominate the specific part of carbon fiber surface energy. Lindsay et al. [11] have also shown that carbon fiber surface hydroxyl groups have the most influence on the ΔG^{SP} values of polar probes and the ΔG^{SP} relates to the γ_s^{SP} of carbon fiber as can be seen from the section 2.

Fig.4 The γ_s^{SP} of carbon fibers as a function of (A) oxygen concentration, (B) O and N concentration, (C) oxides area and (D) peak 2 concentration.

In general there is reasonable agreement between the specific surface energy and Ka values of carbon fibers, as shown in figure 5. The correlation of Ka with oxygen concentration was better than that with total nitrogen and oxygen concentration. The reason may be concluded that the chemical functionalities of nitrogen were heterocyclic structure and show little acidic properties. Interestingly, unlike the specific surface energy, the Ka values plotted to the oxides area showed improved correlation than to the concentration of peak 2 ($R^2=0.991$). The carbon fiber surface carbon-oxygen groups maybe consist of the basic (pyrone), neural (quinine) and acidic groups (carboxylic and hydroxyl groups). The carboxylic groups show strong acidic property than the hydroxyl groups. So, even carboxylic groups content is poor on the carbon fiber surface, they have the most influence on the acidity of the fiber.

Fig.5 The K_a of carbon fibers as a function of (A) oxygen concentration, (B) O and N concentration, (C) oxides area and (D) peak 2 concentration.

4. Conclusions

The γ_s^D , γ_s^{SP} and the acidity-basicity properties of a series of carbon fibers were examined by using the technique of inverse gas chromatography. The relationship between the surface chemistry, surface energy and the acidity-basicity properties of carbon fibers had been investigated. The results indicated that the γ_s^D of a series of commercially sized carbon fiber ranged from 31.02 mJ/m² to 33.11 mJ/m² and showed no obvious correlations with its surface composition. The γ_s^{SP} of the carbon fibers changed considerably from 5.44 mJ/m² to 17.61 mJ/m² and increased with increasing the oxygen percentage ($R^2=0.773$), the oxides area ($R^2=0.982$) and the concentration ($R^2=0.998$). A strong correlation between the γ_s^{SP} and the percentage singly oxygen-containing groups present on the carbon fiber surface was obtained. The carbon fibers were found to exhibit a dominant acidic nature. A reasonable agreement tendency between the γ_s^{SP} and K_a values of carbon fibers was found. The carboxylic groups have the most influence on the acidity of the fiber and a better correlation between the K_a with the oxides area was observed.

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